

Towards a Conquest of Emotionality

Harun Kaygan, Middle East Technical University, Department of Industrial Design – Türkiye

Abstract

As emotions and emotional experiences have become the focus of recent design arguments, a number of approaches have been introduced by scholars from various disciplines. However, neither the quantity nor the scope of those propositions seem sufficient regarding the variety of potential modes of relating design to emotions.

This article aims to review and criticize these existent approaches on the grounds of, firstly, their resemblance to the way in which advertising handles the product and emotion relationship. Secondly, a critique is directed at the false scientism underlying a number of attempts to relate design and emotion. And eventually, through the first two critiques, the article points at the role of 'design and emotion' movement as an agent of design activity to add another layer of rationalization to the subject-object relationship.

Ultimately the article attempts to offer an alternative locating of design and emotion by shifting the emphasis from such rationalization of user-product / subject-object relation towards the effective communication of the 'intended effect' of the design activity and its political character.

Keywords: Design criticism, design research, advertising and product design

Introduction

As both the design activity and the notion of emotionality gained importance and influence in the daily life of the 21st century individual, the question of design and emotion has become an even more central one. What this article aims, in this regard, is to reevaluate the one side of this relation that relates the designer to the emotions as the one that acts upon the latter in a number of ways. This number, however, couldn't keep pace with the sharp increase in the amount of studies directed on design and emotion. Therefore, to criticize existent approaches as well as to propose another one, this paper will attempt to start from a scratch and inquire into how design relates to emotions.

Emotions as Social Phenomena

It seems agreeable to a great extent that emotions themselves are not designable; they are the givens of any design problem rather than the aim. Even when declared as the purpose of an exercise, still they qualify as the external factors to the final product, as observable in studies regarding the 'emotion-aware office chair' (Overbeeke, Vink and Cheung, 2001) or the 'emotion-detecting alarm clock' (Wensween and Overbeeke, 2001) to name a few. The ground for such approaches is that emotions are acknowledged as belonging to the

impenetrable internality of the individual. As biologically and psychologically situated 'fact's, it is solely their outburst that is considered observable. However, such a comprehension of emotions has its roots in the accepted private/public distinction of the society and is, of course, essentially an historical one. (Harding and Pribhram, 2002) And within their historicity, emotions are also culturally-specific as already revealed by propositions regarding *kansei* (Lee, Harada and Stappers, 1999) and *amae* (Kaizuka, 2004), which are not mere translations of 'western' emotions into a new language, but rather distinct definitions and related conceptions emerged under distinctive cultural and historical conditions.

Defined as such, emotions are no more ultimately subjective responses, on the contrary they are culturally constructed and furthermore, they are means for constructing the subjectivity of the individual. (Harding and Pribhram, 2002) Thus, any intervention or action upon emotions is far from being apolitical, including those by media, advertising and, of course, design.

Advertising and emotions

Advertising, in this regard, has already been utilizing emotions and experiences alike to promote products ever since it has surpassed the limits of mere announcements. As early as 1916, Coca-Cola was mentioning the “pleasure of thirst”, while a Jordan motor car advertisement dating back to 1919 was concerned with the “erotic-experiential” pleasure of driving. (Falk, 1994) It was not too long before such practices of attaching images, ideas or feelings to products became a routine of advertising.

This exercise of corresponding products to emotional experiences -and vice versa- as they are marketed soon involved a creatively high number of emotional situations beside mere pleasure, such as confidence (“Witty, confident, devastatingly feminine: Chanel No15”), security (“Promise, confidence, security: Helifax”), happiness (“Happiness Foam-In-Hair Color”) or attention (“She claimed attention with her clean skin: LenPak Cleansing Lotion”) (Williamson, 1978) as well as negative ones like aggression, fear, social incompetence and sadness. But even when the advertisement utilizes the latter, it almost always has to conclude positively, for it is the way in which the advertisement should eventually relate to the product. (Falk, 1994)

Being aware of the fact that all advertising cannot be molded into a singular structure, still it seems that semiotics may prove useful in revealing the engagement between advertising and

emotions during such routines; in order to take reference for further inquiry into the relation between design and emotion. The correspondence between a particular emotion and the product -or whatever is advertised- is, then, primarily a relation of signification. The advertisement attempts to transfer the positively charged meaning embedded in either the whole narrative or its any particular element onto the object of the advertisement; most of the time through blank juxtaposition. So the product is made a signifier of that emotional meaning; to the extent that the product is almost that meaning itself. (Williamson, 1978)

However easily observable it is, the assertion above is not yet sufficient. According to Williamson (1978) the collapse of the signifier and the signified that occurs as the product becomes emotion is more deep-going than sole correspondence, because it is a reciprocal relation where not only the product is defined by the emotion, but also the emotion is defined through the product. An overt illustration of the latter case may be offered by automobile advertising where the 'mere' pleasure evoked in the user by the activity of driving is transcended to the 'pleasure of driving' which refers to a specialized emotional experience. This experience, in this case, is some sort of pleasure associated with, and even defined through, the act of driving. In advertising this is amplified to the extent that the pleasure of driving automobile A is effectively differentiated from the pleasure gained through driving automobile B, yet not only quantitatively, but qualitatively as well. In this manner, the product generates its particular emotional experience, which is achieved only through obtainment -purchase- and possession -use- of the product.

Figure 1, Example for a generic 'pleasure of driving' from Ethyl Gasoline advertisement, "Have you forgotten *the fun of driving?*" (Emphasis added.)

Figure 2, Example for the experience of driving a specific automobile from Saab 9-5 Aero advertisement, "Aerotic: ... Equally important is ... the way the car interacts with your senses. To find out what that *Aero feeling* is about ... drive it." (Emphasis added.)

Such conduct is part of the meaning making process where the product is promoted as the promise of a particular positive emotion -or the negation of a negative one- and so, capable of making the unattainable feelings attainable by possessing it. Thus the feelings are *reduced* to products and their possession; they are no more object-independent entities summoned by, but those essentially generated by the product itself. (Williamson, 1978)

Figure 3, Example for how advertisements give promises of particular emotions from Dim Pantyhose advertisement, “Dim. For the sheer pleasure of it.”

This degradation in the experiencing of emotions is not peculiar to the ways of the advertising, indeed. Similar ways of corresponding emotional experiences to products as generators of engaging interactions and emotional experiences have been facilitated by designers both earlier than and independent from the acknowledgment of design and emotion as a movement, for instance, as early as Alessi or as market-oriented as Koziol. But in addition to these designers and companies who have consciously aimed at emotional experiences as such, similar patterns can be observed in the whole discipline of design activity. The reason is that meanings employed by the advertisements and the design of any product are derived from a higher semiotic source, which is almost the same pool of signs for both professions. This higher grid of meanings, in which interrelated products assemble into wider clusters of meaning, are often named “ambiences” or “atmospheres,” (Baudrillard, 1970) each of which, conventionally mentioned as 'hot', 'fun', 'cool', 'dark' etc. corresponds to a particular emotional experience. Most of the products are not only marketed but -

consciously or not- designed as well according to these schemes, similar to the emotion-product relation in advertisements revealed above.

However, this mode of relating design and emotional experience is in stark contrast with the aspirations of design and emotion, which have been towards “emotionally rich interactions” (Wensveen and Overbeeke, 2001) so far; for through such an approach the outcome of the design activity may not accomplish more than giving away reckless promises of marketable experiences.

So corporate strategies may be criticized on the grounds that they decide on the emotional resonances of an object by means of its design (Cupchik, 2004) and even reduce some emotional concepts to products and related ambiences, but such a critique may look rather superficial, though not lacking significance, unless it is exposed to a further inquiry into the underlying ideological functions of design activity.

Design as an agent of rational reassembling of subject-object pair

Design is, first of all, the modern counterpart of making daily objects, with which people interact in their everyday lives, and designers are those involved in especially the occupation of preconceiving these objects. But, of course, design, being a strictly historical phenomenon, is not without the responsibilities put in advance by the modern society, such as compatibility with mass production related issues, or with what is called the market demand. On the contrary, it owes its existence as today to the rationalized production and the political economy that accompanies it: it is considered efficient -or profitable- to the degree that it is successfully adapted to production and consumption on rational terms.

In its historicity, thus, design is essentially a rational process, but furthermore part of an attempt to rationalize the totality of the environment by re-establishing subject-object relationship on a rational basis. (Baudrillard, 1981) Kurtgozu (2003) has, in this regard, presented a history of this relationship in three stages, together with the parallel design attitudes. The first stage is governed by instrumental reason, which subordinated objects to the dominating subject and gave birth to Bauhaus functionalism, and ergonomics, striving to act upon the universal subject. The second stage by the 60s was a reversal of the balance, with the consumer culture on the rise accompanied by styling in the design communities, bringing the domination of the object over the subject. And finally the third stage, starting

with the 90s, is the celebration of the reciprocity between subject and object where the product semantics and design and emotion originates.

Regardless of the positiveness of the argument of a correlation against those of dominance, in any period mentioned there is a reestablished relation between subject and object, and according to Baudrillard (1981) this was started when Bauhaus first disassembled the subject-object pair in order to reassemble it into a functionally connected pair. Most of the remaining discourses developed on and for design activity have been variations on this theme, and thus far have proved quite beneficial for providing grounds and justification for what designers have done, but not further enough to develop an alternative view. For instance, ergonomic articulation between subject and object is based on measurability and the semantic one on communication. Eventually design and emotion may be destined to be another mode of reassembling the subject-object pair in terms of emotionality and experience.

For example, both the 'emotion-detecting alarm clock' (Wensveen and Overbeeke, 2001) and the 'emotion-aware office chair' (Overbeeke, Vink and Cheung, 2001) may be criticized for being major attempts towards this kind of a re-assemblage. These products aim to rationally reproduce the normally subjective and relative, thus highly complex, behavioral patterns of the user through a design approach which almost resembles the design of a computer program in order to categorize and guess those patterns. Though both projects are quite admirable for their user-centered and organic approaches to the interfaces, the fact that they employ smartness of the product for solving the complexity involved in the rational reassembling of subject-object pairs leaves them vulnerable for the critique directed towards previous approaches above.

The issue here is not that these approaches were not sufficiently 'idealistic' but that they have tended to become almost mere styles convenient for marketing purposes, as soon as they were taken away from the mode of subject-object relation they belonged to. How the hardly acquired public consciousness for sustainable development has been degraded to green design all over again through excessive manipulation by advertising and marketing is one example, while the way in which ergonomics has become a stylistic concern for toothbrushes and sandals is another. (Berkman, 2001) Therefore a new design approach that regards emotionality of the user may seem sufficient at the first glance, however it demands much more attentive criticism to be able to avoid such digestion by the consumer market.

Design and inadequate scientism

Rationalization of the subject-object relation finds its uttermost expression in the improper scientism evident in research on emotional aspects of design. PrEmo -an instrument developed for measuring the emotional effects of product design (Desmet, 1999)- is, in this regard, a highly problematic proposal including a number of methodical handicaps. These problems are especially those regarding the consistency and reliability of the responses of the subjects of the experiment. For instance, the readability of the symbolic animations of the PrEmo character is highly doubtful, not only cross-culturally but between various social layers within a particular society. Furthermore, the corresponding emotion definitions themselves, within arbitrary classifications, do not qualify as sufficiently exact for being accepted as the givens of an adequately scientific research.

Such critiques directed towards a particular study, however, remain superficial unless they are situated against the notion of scientism itself. In order to accomplish this, previously mentioned concept of design as an occupation may be further elaborated. Because design is a work, an occupation, it is of the everyday life. It is neither the 'art' nor the 'science' of making objects, for art and science are mere means which provide everyday thinking with the 'objectifications' to make it easier to deal with daily problems (Lukacs, 1978). Lukacs further argues that daily occupations are usually closer to either side -either art or science- and they seldom even become successful in arts or sciences; but this situation is not to be evaluated as an enhancement of the work towards a more adequate objectification, rather it is a transfer of evaluation criteria from arts or sciences into that particular product of occupation, in this case the design activity.

The fact that evaluation of everyday objects on the scientific level is not an exceptional case, is due to the role of science today as the only 'dependable' source of truth. Berkman (2002) associates this problem, this time in the context of criticizing ergonomics as a style, with the "technology-driven progressivism that dominates the western civilization."

An alternative approach

Thus far this paper has attempted a criticism by designating what is to be avoided as design acts upon emotions and emotional experiences. One problematic relation regards the market: as products are not only advertised but also designed as commodified emotional experiences,

design and emotion risks being vanished into just another marketing strategy for providing related parties with marketable experiences and ambiances. Designs that aim to express particular emotions or propose new experiences closely resemble advertising language and may be readily digested by the market dynamics for easy consumption.

Another criticism asserted is about the way in which design is grounded upon -and justified in turn by- various aspects of the relationship between the user and the product, subject and object. Especially in design research, the subject-object totality is detached, rationally captured and posited. In emotional product design, similarly, there seems a tendency to crack open the experience of the user by making it subject to a detailed inspection. When it is attempted to reassemble the subject-object pair, rationalized and categorized, the experience is already synthetically modified.

One last similar trapdoor is located under the scientific 'looks' of design research, at the point when it strikingly resembles ergonomics research methods, which are directed -in essence- towards a universal subject. Such misplacement implies inadequate scientism applied to design and emotion research, in order to, consciously or not, scientize the design activity in parallel with the dominant prejudices regarding science, technology and progress.

Marketing orientation and rationalization of design process condemned as inappropriate for the present aspirations of the 'design and emotion' movement, proposing an alternative approach becomes obligatory. However, for the limits of this paper prohibit detailed examination of the argument, it will be considered sufficient to assert and emphasize a few points towards a new understanding of the relation between design and emotion, leaving many question marks open for further research.

In order to define such an approach Lukacs' arguments mentioned above will be reconsulted where Lukacs (1978) presents rhetoric as an example of everyday occupations, among which design activity, as the occupation of making daily objects, was situated earlier. Buchanan (1989) furthers this correspondence to the extent that he considers design an essentially rhetorical activity. In this manner the existence of such a variety of approaches within design discipline is justified (Buchanan, 1995) while a new definition for design activity is introduced which regards design as directed at an 'intended effect' utilizing technology, aesthetics and ethics. (Buchanan, 1989) Together with Lukacs' arguments, this reveals a valuable schema where design is located as an occupation between science and art, while

technology, as a carrier of scientific objectifications, and emotions, as a carrier of artistic objectifications, are means for design activity to reach the intended effect. This construction leads to two noteworthy consequences:

1. Design guided by emotional experiences may be criticized similar to the way in which Buchanan (1989) objects the dominance of technology as an end-in-itself during the design of everyday objects. That is because emotions are not ends-in-themselves as well, and may not be the *aim* of the product. Rather, they are means for the design process in reaching its particular intended effect.
2. Even if the intended effect of a design is as simple as to persuade the user to buy the product, the third means for the design activity, the ethical considerations, makes the final intended effect inevitably a political one, involving an ethical, therefore a political choice. Design activity thus becomes a process of active political contemplation instead of mere application of scientific and aesthetic criteria.

Conclusion

Once the emphasis of design diverted from subject-object relations towards a political rhetoric and the political value of emotions adequately addressed, 'design and emotion' movement may change course towards a politically aware approach, by which design and designers will be encouraged to explore and act upon the essentially political reflections of public/private, feminine/masculine etc. differentiations in the emotion definitions of the society. Therefore, the scope of future design studies offered by this article anticipates a critical moment where it will be revealed if the aspirations of 'design and emotion' are towards a conquest of emotionality or onto new spaces of action and contemplation for design practitioners.

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Harun Kaygan is currently a M.Sc. student in the Department of Industrial Design at Middle East Technical University (METU). His primary research interests are design criticism and ontology of design; with an ongoing research on the evaluation criteria and related vocabularies shared by product design communities.